

DETERMINATION OF THE SHRINKAGE LIMIT FROM THE BRITISH FALL CONE FLOW INDEX

Gerald Maregesi

Email: gerald.maregesi@aesi.co.tz

ABSTRACT

Determining the shrinkage limit using the mercury or wax method is time-consuming and error-prone. This paper presents a model that uses a British cone flow index to compute the shrinkage limit of the soil. The model was developed based on the analysis of 186 Atterberg limits test results from the literature leading to the formulation of an equation for computing the shrinkage limit of the soil using the British fall cone flow index.

INTRODUCTION

The shrinkage limit is one of the Atterberg limits and, in most cases, is the lowest limit, while the liquid limit is the largest limit. The mercury method is the most common method of determining the shrinkage limit (BS 1377:Part 2:1990, AASHTO T92-88, ASTM D427-98). Mercury is an expensive and hazardous material. The alternative method to ASTM D427-98 is ASTM D4943-02 which uses wax instead of mercury, but both methods are operator-dependent and time-consuming. Therefore, in most cases, the method proposed by Casagrande of estimating the shrinkage limit based on the U-line and A-line is frequently used in calculating the shrinkage limit of the soil. This method was reported to be close to the determined values of the shrinkage limit [Holtz and Kovacs (1981), cited by Kayabali(2012)]

Several alternative methods have been proposed to determine the shrinkage limit, such as sand replacement, wax method, and reverse extrusion, to improve the accuracy of the mercury method [Cerato (2006), Prakash and Sridharan (2011), Prakash and Sridharan (2012), Kayabali (2015)]. Maregesi(2022) proposed equations for computing the shrinkage limit using the British fall cone slope or the plasticity index of the soil.

It has been reported that the shrinkage limit of the soil does not depend on the plasticity of the

soil. The main factor affecting the shrinkage limit is the grain size distribution and fabric [Sridharan & Rao (1971), Sridharan & Prakash (2000), Kayabali &Yaldiz (2015)]. However, the method of estimating the shrinkage limit of the soil proposed by Casagrande and the one proposed by Maregesi (2022) suggest that the shrinkage limit depends on the plasticity of the soil.

The equation of computing shrinkage limits using the British fall cone flow index is presented in this paper. Since the fall cone flow index is a measure of soil plasticity [Sridharan *et al.* (1999)], then the shrinkage limit of the soil is a characteristic property of the soil. The proposed models were developed based on an analysis of 186 shrinkage limit test results collected from the literature.

THE BRITISH FALL CONE FLOW INDEX

The flow index is the slope of a linear relationship between the water content and the \log_{10} (depth of the penetration in mm). Since the slope of the British flow decreases as the moisture content decreases, Maregesi (2022) proposed the flow index to be computed using equation 1.

$$I_{fc} = \frac{W_{25} - W_5}{\log 25 - \log 5} \dots \dots (1)$$

Where

I_{fc} is the flow index, W_{25} and W_5 are the water content corresponding to 25 mm and 5 mm penetration, respectively.

ANALYSIS OF SHRINKAGE LIMIT DATA FROM LITERATURE

186 Atterberg limits data were collected from literature and analyzed [Cerrato & Lutenegger (2006), Prakash & Sridharan (2011), Prakash & Sridharan (2012), Kayabali (2012), Kayabali & Yaldiz(2012), Prakash *et al.* (2015) and Vincent *et al.* (2021)]. The first step in data analysis involved modeling the flow curve in the form shown in equation 2. The slope of the flow curve

was computed using equation 3 [Maregesi (2022)]. After that, the water content corresponding to 25 mm and 5 mm penetration was computed. Eventually, the flow index was calculated using equation 1.

$$y = mx + c \dots (x) \dots (2)$$

$$m = \frac{21.7783}{I_p^{0.9579}} - 0.0354 \dots (3)$$

The data analysis indicates that the fall cone flow index is highly correlated to the shrinkage index of the soil, defined as the arithmetic difference between the liquid limit and the shrinkage limit (LL-SL), as shown in Figure 1 ($R^2=0.9894$). Therefore, the flow index can be used to compute the shrinkage index of the soil using equation 4.

$$S_i = LL - SL = 4.133(I_{fc} - 8.549)^{0.7075} \dots (4)$$

Figure 1: Relationship between the fall cone flow index and shrinkage index ($R^2=0.9894$)

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the plot of an equation proposed by Maregesi (2022) for computing the plasticity index using the British fall cone flow index and equation 4 proposed in this study for calculating the shrinkage index using the fall cone flow index. Based on this analysis of shrinkage limit data, it can be seen that at a low plasticity index of about 20, the shrinkage limit and plastic limit are very close. At a plasticity index of about 10, the plastic limit and the shrinkage limit are the same, while at a plasticity index of less than 10,

the shrinkage limit may be higher than the plastic limit. It can also be seen that the change of shrinkage index and change of the plasticity index at diverse fall cone flow index follows the same pattern suggesting that the shrinkage index depends on the plasticity of the soil.

Figure 2: comparison between the plasticity index and shrinkage index and diverse values of fall cone flow index

Figure 3: Residual analysis

Figure 3 shows a residual analysis for the fitted data using equation 4 compared to the conventional mercury method. Figure 4 shows a comparison between the determined and computed shrinkage limit, while Figure 5 shows the residual histogram of the fitted data. It can be seen that 87% of the results are within the statistical bound ± 6.8 given in AASHTO T92-88

as multi-laboratory precision for two results obtained from two properly conducted tests of the same type for the mercury displacement method. Hence, the shrinkage limit values obtained from the mercury displacement method and the one computed using equation 4 are within acceptable statistical bounds.

Figure 4: Comparison between determined and computed shrinkage limit

Figure 5: Residual histogram

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The conventional method of determining the shrinkage limit of soil involves the use of mercury, which is a hazardous health substance. The equation proposed for computing the shrinkage limit using the fall cone flow index can be used to compute the shrinkage limit since the

results obtained from the proposed equation are in good agreement with those from the conventional mercury displacement method and within acceptable statistical bounds. The main advantage of the proposed model is that all Atterberg limits can be computed in a single operation of determination of the liquid limit using the British fall cone. This study suggests that the shrinkage limit is a plasticity property of the soil.

References:

1. American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (1988), Standard Method of Test for Determining the Shrinkage Factors of Soils, AASHTO T92-88
2. American Society for Testing Materials, 1998, Standard Test Method for Shrinkage factor of soils by the mercury method: ASTM D427-98.
3. American Society for Testing Materials, 2002, Standard Test Method for Shrinkage factor of soils by the wax method: ASTM D43937-02.
4. BSI, BS 1377: part 2: 1990, British Standard methods of test for soil for engineering purpose. Part 2: Classification tests, BSI, London
5. Cerato, A, Lutenegeger A.J, (2006), shrinkage of clays, Proceedings of the 4th International conference on unsaturated soils: Phoenix, AZ, April 2-6. GSP No, 147.1:1097-1108.
6. Holtz, R.D, Kovacs, W.D, (1981), An introduction to geotechnical engineering: Prentice Hall, NJ, 733 pp
7. Maregesi, G (2022), determination of the plasticity index using slope of the fall cone flow curve, Advanced Engineering Solutions Journal, Vol 2/22
8. Maregesi, G (2022), computation of shrinkage limit using the slope of fall cone flow curve, Advanced Engineering Solutions Journal, Vol 2/22
9. determination of the plasticity index using slope of the fall cone flow curve, Advanced Engineering Solutions Journal, Vol 2/22

10. Kayabali, K, Yaldiz, Ö, Investigation of the relationship between swell pressure and shrinkage limit, *Electronic Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, January 2015
11. Kayabali, K (2012), Estimation of Liquid, Plastic and Shrinkage limits using one Simple Tool, *Electronic Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, January 2012
12. Sridharan, A & Prakash, K (2000), Shrinkage limit of soil mixture, *Geotechnical testing journal* 23(1)3-8
13. Sridharan, A & Prakash, K (1998), Mechanism controlling the shrinkage limit of soils: *Geotechnical Testing Journal*, 240-250
14. Sridharan, A, Nagaraj, H.B, Prakash, K, (1999) Determination of the Plasticity Index from Flow index, *Geotechnical testing journal*, GTJODJ, Vol 22, No.2 June 1999, pp 169-175
15. Prakash, K & Sridharan, A, (2012) use of uniform and inert beads for the determination of shrinkage limit of fine grains soils, *Geotech Geol Eng*
16. Prakash, K, Sridhran, A, Karthik, H.K & Anand, C (2011), Sand replacement method for determination of the shrinkage limit, *Journal of Hazardous, toxic and radioactive waste*, Vol.15 No.2, ASCE
17. Prakash, K, Sridharan, A, Baba, A.J, Thejas H.K (2008), determination of the Shrinkage limit of fine grained materials by wax method, *Geotechnical testing journal*, Vol. 32, No. 1
18. Vincent, N.A, Shivashankar, R, Lokesh, K.N, (2021) Nath, D, Shrinkage Limit Studies from Moisture Content: Electrical Resistivity Relationship of soils, *Arabian Journal of Science and Engineering*, <http://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-020-05325-5>.
19. Nitterberg, F. (1982): *Geotechnical Properties and Behaviour of Calcretes in South and Southwest Africa. Geotechnical Properties, Behaviour, and Performance of Calcareous Soils. ASTM STP 777. American Society for Testing and Materials*, pp. 296–309.
20. Nagaraj, T.S.; Srinivasa Murthy, B.R.: A critical reappraisal of compression index equations. *Geotechnique* 36(1), 135–138 (1986)